

Report on the SNSF project Agora CRAG-1_145640
Veni, Vidi... Ludique. Games and Toys in Roman Antiquity
(2013-2016)

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<https://lettres.unifr.ch/fr/hist/histoire-de-lart-et-archeologie/recherche/agora.html>

Executive summary

The project *Veni, vidi, ludique* was developed as planned at the University of Fribourg by Véronique Dasen and Ulrich Schädler in order to present the results of the latest research on games and toys in Graeco-Roman antiquity in three Swiss museums. From May 2014 until February 2016 each museum presented different aspects of the sources and artefacts, placed in their cultural context. The exhibitions at the three museums share the same common title, but have distinct subtitles according to their specialty:

- 1. Nyon, Roman Museum (MRN):** “The game of life” (the role of games in the life cycle), May 24 - October 31, 2014.
- 2. La Tour-de-Peilz, Swiss Museum of Games (MSJ):** “Playing with antiquity” (the reception of antiquity in board games), October 10, 2014 – extended until April 19, 2015.
- 3. Vallon, Roman Museum (MRV):** “The die is cast” (on the rules of board games with workshops), March 14, 2015 – extended until February 28, 2016.

The aim was to make available and share an important material and intangible cultural heritage with a wide audience. In a historical and anthropological perspective, the aim was to engage wider reflection on gender and stereotypes of gendered roles (dolls for girls, carts for boys?), religion (toys and rites of passage; games and divination), adult/child relationship, educational principles and more generally models of socialisation and transmission of cultural values. In order to make active visitors of all ages, promote the transmission of knowledge and reflections, we planned to develop new tools beside traditional ones : mixing guided tours of the exhibitions, open days, public demonstrations and practice, workshops with children and adults, with new technologies, smartguides (QR codes) with complementary material for an interactive guided tour on mobile phone, short videos on demand with reconstructed games, touchtables with games. Public debates, lectures and courses also aimed at fostering new reflections among students and researchers.

Introduction

The background of the activity

Since many years, the main applicant, Véronique Dasen, Professor of classical art and archaeology at Fribourg university, has been working on the material culture of childhood and youth, uncovering new informations and revising a number of commonplaces thanks to an interdisciplinary approach (archaeological, literary, historical, philological, and anthropological). The co-applicant, PD Dr Ulrich Schädler, leads also since many years innovative researches on ancient games, especially boardgames. As Director of the *Swiss Museum of Game* (MSJ) in La Tour-de-Peilz since 2002, he organises annual exhibitions on games, both ancient and modern, and promotes a new vision of the place occupied by games in ancient and present societies thanks to exhibitions, events, and publications.

The team was completed by two museums that already collaborated together, the *Roman Museum* in Nyon and the *Roman Museum* in Vallon (exchanges of exhibitions), and also separately with the main and co-applicants (scientific collaborations to exhibitions, *Festival international du film d'archéologie de Nyon*). The project represented for the first time a large joint collaborative effort that developed in a very fruitful way.

Why this project ?

Few exhibitions have been devoted to ancient games and toys, often seen as childish and minor occupations. Long regarded as a marginal field of research, ancient games and toys represent in fact an important cultural heritage from antiquity, engaging wider reflection on our present society. Games and toys provide a wealth of information on gender and stereotypes on gendered roles (dolls for girls, carts for boys?), religion, such as games and divination, adult/child relationship, educational principles, and more generally models of socialisation and transmission of cultural values.

More reflection is needed on the relation between the culture of play and the transformation of western systems of values. Major changes in the notion, theory and practice of play and games took place since Antiquity. Recent publications on the passage from the Age of Enlightenment and the rise of the bourgeoisie society to the turn of 20th-21st century have shown the impact of political, social, economic and cultural changes in society: games are modified or entirely dismissed, others appear or are revaluated. The overall approach towards games is changing: more or less time is devoted to games; play is institutionalized; games are used in education; gambling is popular/condemned; etc. At present, games are omnipresent (in the media, on computers and mobile phones, etc.) and the gambling industry flourishes; games seem to invade adult life in a way that was not possible a generation ago.

What you hoped to achieve and why,

The aim was to promote in-depth questioning of a wide audience about the place of ludic culture in past and present societies, implying reflecting on norms, social habits and developmental needs.

The results of the latest researches, with the revision of a number of misconceptions, had to me made available for the first time to the public in various forms. We also wished to promote an original and fruitful area of research that could involve a new generation of young researchers.

The aims and objectives of the activities

The aim was to communicate widely scientific knowledge and promote research. Our target audience involved different partners from town and university, especially:

- Children from the primary school onwards
- Parents and other members of the family who can transmit knowledge on past toys and games
- Immigrant families acquainted with their traditional culture of play
- Teachers who use games and toys in the educational system
- Professionals in the field of education/psychology
- Archaeologists as well as other specialists of the ancient world, also on an international level (researchers, professors in ancient history, art history, philology, anthropology) for exchanging and redistributing new assets.
- Associations of players (ancient and modern games), and toy lending libraries.

Methods

In order to involve actively a wide audience, of adults and children, specialists and non-specialists, from town and university, events of different nature aimed at turning visitors into actors of the exhibition.

A first set of *traditional methods* made the public familiar with the ancient ludic environment

- the display of objects in the exhibitions allowed a much appreciated direct, material, contact with authentic, rare and precious items, like ivory dolls or wheel-horses.
- a traditional method of « Learning by doing » was promoted in museum spaces with games to play. A great effort was put on very successful workshops with public demonstrations in various spaces (museums, town, university), also with associations of players.
- A « Roman » dice game, Ludix, was invented in 2014 by U. Schädler, in collaboration with Niek Neuwahl and the Society Piatnik. It won an international Austrian price in 2015 (see below).
- A more specialised audience was reached thanks to courses, lectures, doctoral workshops, and international conferences.

- an interactive leporello-catalogue was made for the MRN, a booklet with boardgames inspired by antiquity in the MSJ, and a booklet with rules illustrated in the MRV.
- Educational documentation was provided for children and teachers in each museum (*dossier pédagogique*), available in print and to download. The content of the documentation aimed also at making children interactive with the exhibited material (video, games...), with discovery trails with questions.

New technologies represent the second methodological set employed for promoting an active transmission of knowledge:

- smartguides (QR codes), realised with the society Apiness software, provided a wealth of information in each museum (pictures, texts, audio, and short videos with ethnographic parallels or interviews) that could be seen on the Iphone and/or visited again on our website venividiludique (especially appreciated by those, still many, who are not yet familiar with the QRcodes technology) (see details below)
- 4 table touch animations, partly realised with the society Apiness software, partly with private informaticians, with interactive simulations, made users actively understand the know-how, rules and meanings of ancient games and techniques. The Oracle of knucklebone was especially liked by visitors (who can send the oracle by email from the touchtable in the museum). It is freely available on App store (see details below)

As planned, we launched, a call for development of ancient games. Three students from the Haute Ecole Arc Ingénierie, St-Imier (Danick Fort, Gary Nietlispach, Matthieu Rossier) developed a version of ludus Latrunculorm, now available on AppStore. More financial means would however be necessary to have a fully satisfying product.

<https://play.google.com/store/apps/details?id=ch.hearc.mercenary>

- 7 short movies were realised with children from Fribourg playing ancient games, dressed like Romans, They are a great popular success. They provided an unexpected life to ancient rules, enlivening iconographic representations, displaying ancient gestures and dexterity. Modern viewers could project themselves in the past, especially children warmly responded to these videos that were projected in each museum, and at the *Festival International du film de Nyon* in 2015. (see details below)

Structure of the remainder of the report

1. Milestones
2. Presentation of the main events with wide audiences
3. Collaborations
4. Prizes/Distinctions
5. Communication with media
6. International conferences
7. Outputs (publications, Public and scientific lectures)
8. Major Outputs
9. Measurable output
10. Description of the content
11. Google analytics

1. The milestones were achieved according to the planned schedule:

Phases 1-2, 1st March 2013 until May 24, 2014: bibliographic research, selection of the objects for loans (11 museums in Switzerland, 7 in France, 2 in Italy). Creation of a common scenographic and graphic line with Sven Tugwell (scenography) and Hélène Becquelin (graphism). These two specialists created an original common visual line used in various ways in the three exhibitions, inspired by Roman representations of games as well as by an illustration of modern board game.

Distributing the topics between the 3 museums. Organising the MRN exhibition and events, planning MSJ events. Elaborating, writing and editing the MRN exhibition (14 panels, 13 'More about' files, 11 QR codes, with animations, audio texts, a leporello catalogue). Selecting the pictures of the panels, including 10 neon panels. Preparing teaching material and multimedia material: 4 table-touch animations, 1 booklet with reconstructed rules of ancient games, 1 paedagogical handout for children and teachers, 1 praxinoscope. Preparing the paedagogical space with 5 ancient games and their rules.

Seven short movies were realised with children from Fribourg reconstructing ancient games by François Vermot (with partial financial support of Fribourg University, *Fonds de recherche*).

We also edited a special issue of *Archeothema* (31, 2013), a wide audience journal, on *Games and Toys in Antiquity*, with contributions of international experts, with a video interview and available for download on tablets and iPhones: <http://www.archeothema.com/numero/jeux-et-jouets-greco-romains.htm>
In parallel: scientific contribution to the exhibition in Augusta Raurica *Kinder? Kinder! Auf Spurensuche in Augusta Raurica (2013-2016)*.

Creation of the website venividiludique.ch, with a facebook page, as well as a special webpage at Fribourg university on the Agora project, recording and advertising all events:

<https://lettres.unifr.ch/fr/hist/histoire-de-lart-et-archeologie/recherche/agora.html>

Since January 2014: Jubilee 12th anniversary of Fribourg University with many activities promoting the Agora project: Creation of an additional exhibition at Fribourg university on Games and Toys of Yesterday and Today, with two QR codes, guided visits of this exhibition, Demonstrations of games in the Roadshow and other events at University and outside. Organising the Journée Portes ouvertes, of the Institut du monde antique et byzantin on the theme “Jouer avec l’Antiquité” (October 4, 2014), with demos, guided visit, projection of movies.

Phase 3, until October 10, 2014: preparing the MSJ exhibition (researching objects, selecting material for the exhibition, writing and editing 9 panels, 6 QR codes, 1 booklet on modern games about Antiquity), selecting board games to play in the exhibition area, as well as 2 video games. Creation of Ludix, a dice game (Austrian award 2015, Wiener Spieleakademie).

Organising events at the MRN (Journée Portes ouvertes, guided visits, *café scientifique* “Rêve de poupées” with Marie-Noëlle Favre, Swiss artist; a movie was made with interviews of visitors by Chr. Goumand.

Starting planning the MRV exhibition.

Phase 4, until March 14 2015: preparing the MRV exhibition (8 panels, 6 QR codes, 7 Roman games and rules available in the exhibition area), 1 booklet with illustrated rules, 8 watercolours by H. Becquelin.

Organising events in the MSJ: an international conference *Jeux et multiculturalité*, supported by the SNF (20.-22.10.2014), two *cafés scientifiques* with an anthropologist of game, Roberte Hamayon (21.9.2014), with a historian of toys, Michel Manson (25.2.2015), two meetings of creator of games inspired by Antiquity, Bruno Cathala, *Cyclades*, (9.12.2014), Spartaco Albertarelli, *SPQRisk* (20.2.2015), and several workshops with games inspired by antiquity).

Roman Museum, Vallon, opening of “The die is cast”, March 2015

Carmen Buchiller, Head of the *Service Archeologique de l’Etat de Fribourg*, Jean-Pierre Siggen, Conseiller d’Etat, Fribourg, Véronique Dasen, University of Fribourg, Clara Agustoni, curator, Roman Museum Vallon

Phase 5, until February 28, 2016: Organising events at MRV (Journée Portes ouvertes, June 28, 2015, *café scientifique* “Osselets et mémoire ludique”, with Thierry Wendling, Paris).

Organising the 18th Board Games studies conference 15-18.4.2015 (MSJ-Fribourg University with visits of the MSJ and MRV exhibitions).

The last *café scientifique* took place at Fribourg university on december 9, 2015, “Jeux interdits”, with Pascal Pichonnaz and Claudia Dubuis, Lausanne.

In parallel : organising the new exhibition in Bavay, Forum antique (17.9.2015 – 19.1.2016), lecturing on games and toys in France (spring 2015 : Angers, autumn 2015 : Paris, EHESS, with two Journées d’études)

2. Presentation of the main events

In order to advertise and record all the events that took place during these two years, we created a website: venividiludique.ch, with a facebook page.

All details are kept there, as well as on the site of Fribourg University:

<https://lettres.unifr.ch/fr/hist/histoire-de-lart-et-archeologie/recherche/agora.html>

Most articles are available on rero.doc or on the academia.edu pages of the authors (E. Clivaz, V. Dasen, U. Schädler).

Main events

During the exhibitions, many guided tours and workshops with children and adults were organised in each museums (see venividiludique.ch). We reduced the number of Cafés scientifiques from 9 to 4, but adding other kind of events, such as 2 meetings of creators of games, workshops with children and adults at Fribourg university during 2014 (Jubilee of the 125th Jubilee anniversary of the university). Events took place in the town of Fribourg. We also had demonstrations and workshops in other museums, such as at the Römertag in Vindonissa, and in Swiss towns (Roadshow). The following main events took place:

Cafés scientifiques

Nyon, Roman Museum

28.6.2014: with the modern 'dolls' of Marie-Noëlle Favre, Swiss artist, and Elodie Clivaz, *Rêver les poupées, hier et aujourd'hui*. ca 120 participants

Chr. Goumand realised a short movie made of interviews of visitors, available on youtube, [venividiludique](http://venividiludique.ch), Fribourg website, and academia.edu: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=qigip59WDOM&feature=youtu.be>

La Tour-de-Peilz, Swiss Museum of Game

21.10.2014: with Roberte Hamayon, Paris, “Un regard d’anthropologue, à la lumière des quatre principes de jeu de Roger Caillois”, moderation Thomas Späth, Bern University: 40 participants.
25.2.2015: with Michel Manson, Toulouse, “Jeux de putti, de l’Antiquité à la Renaissance: les jouets en plus”: 20 participants.

Other events for the general public:

9.12.2014: with Bruno Cathala, creator of the board game *Cyclades*: 15 participants

20.2.2015: with Spartaco Albertarelli, creator of *SPQRisk*: 8 participants

17.04.2015: Games night in collaboration with the Ludothèque La Tour: 12 participants

Regular initiations, one weekend and Wednesday afternoon per month during the exhibitions. Organised with the association Ch’PiiL : 7 months x 2 = 14 x 10 participants = ca 140 participants

Vallon, Roman Museum

28.6.2015: with Thierry Wendling, Paris, “Osselets et mémoire ludique” (among the participants: Clara Agustoni, Elodie Clivaz, Véronique Dasen, François Gauthier, Véronique Pache Huber, Véronique Rey-Vodoz, Ulrich Schädler): 232 participants

Fribourg University

09.12.2015, with Claudia Dubuis, sociologist and Pascal Pichonnaz, Roman Law, Francesca Prescendi, History of Religion, “Jeux interdits”, moderation: Elodie Clivaz and François Gauthier, ca 30 participants.

Jubilee of the 125th anniversary of Fribourg University

During the year 2014, the SNF Agora project was actively involved and promoted in various ways at Fribourg University (jubilee of the University 125th anniversary).

27.2.2014- 15.11.2014 : **Exhibition** „Jeux et jouets d’hier et d’aujourd’hui“ in the University hall, created by E. Clivaz, V. Dasen, C. Pittet (student) and U. Schädler, with regular guided tours.

May-October 2014: **Roadshow**, *Jouer comme au temps des Romains*: the University bus was equipped with a large wooden chest containing Roman boardgames and nuts, with rules written in French, German and Italian by V. Dasen and U. Schädler.

Public demonstrations at each stop of the bus: 4457 participants
<http://www.unifr.ch/news/fr/12301/>

- Fribourg, Place Georges Python (2-10.5)
- Bulle, Place des Alpes (13-24.5)
- Sion, Place de la Planta (3-6.6)
- Guin, Place du centre commercial (gare) (10-14.6)
- Estavayer-le-Lac, Place de l'Amarante (17.-21.6)
- Châtel-St-Denis, Place d'Armes (25-28.6)
- Romont, Place St-Jacques (3.6.9)
- Morat, Berntorplatz (10.13.9)
- Olten, Kirchgasse (16-19.9)
- Delémont, Cour du Château (25-28.9)
- Coire, Kornplatz (1-4.10)
- Lugano, Piazza Castello (8-11.10)

20.9.2014: Pérolles 2, official Feast of the Jubilee, with demonstrations: 8000 participants

Other public demonstrations of *Veni, vidi, ludique*

4.5.2014: *Römertag*, Vindonissa Museum Brugg and Legionärspfad Windisch.
 1618 children, 2015 adults = 3669 participants

4.10.2014: Université de Fribourg, Institut du monde antique et byzantin, Open doors day (over 150 participants).

Morning: demonstration of games

Midday: guided tour of the exhibition at University

Afternoon: Projection of the seven films realised by François Vermot, with the participation of the children who acted in the films.

23-28.3.2015 IX Festival international du film d'archéologie (FIFAN):
 Presentation to the public of the seven films realised for *Veni, vidi, ludique* (category "Hors competition")
Pentelitha, le jeu « des cinq pierres » ; *Pleistobolinda, le jeu « du coup le plus haut »* ; *Omilla, le « jeu du cercle »* ; *Nuces castellatae, les « châteaux de noix »* ; *Noix : Le jeu de la planche* ; *Tropa* ; *Jeu de billes*
<http://www.mrn.ch/fr/festival/edition/en-cours-0-97468>

3. Collaborations

Beside the collaborations associated with the loan of objects from various national and international museums:

GB: panoply.org (loan of an animation movie "Clash of the dicers"; interview with Steve Simons on their site:
<http://panoplyclassicsandanimation.blogspot.ch/2015/08/magic-and-play-panoply-interview-with.html>

I: Milano: research group from Milano *Games in the ancient world* (Sambon collection)

I: Arkimedeion Museum, loan of the loculus of Archimedes

Augusta Raurica, Augst, scientific collaboration (V. Dasen) to the exhibition "Kinder? Kinder! Auf Spurensuche in Augusta Raurica" (2013-2016), directed by Barbara Pfäffli

<http://www.augustaurica.ch/de/besuchen/museum/aktuelle-ausstellung/>

4. Prices/Distinctions

Elodie Clivaz for her master thesis at Fribourg University : *La poupée, un double de la jeune fille ? Pour une réinterprétation de la poupée articulée romaine (IIe-VIIe s. apr. J.-C.)*

Prix d'encouragement de la Fondation pour le Patrimoine culturel, Lausanne, 2015

Prix « Études Genre », Université de Fribourg, 2015

Prix de la Société Académique du Valais, 2015

Ulrich Schädler for the creation of Ludix :

2015 Price of the Wiener Spielakademie, category *Spielehits mit Freunden*.

http://www.spielepreis.at/wordpress/?page_id=474

5. Communication with media: regular interviews with journalists

(contents available as pdf or links to podcasts on www.venividiludique.ch and <https://lettres.unifr.ch/fr/hist/histoire-de-l-art-et-archeologie/recherche/agora.html>)

Radio

Radio Fribourg, interview sur le projet « Veni, vidi, ludique », V. Dasen 16. 1. 2014.

Radio Suisse Romande, *espace 2, Babylone*, « L'histoire de la maternité », V. Dasen, with Nicole Duparc, Nancy Ypsilantis, 7.9.2015.

"Le rendez-vous culture" de Radio Fribourg, C. Agustoni, 17 .3.2015.

Radio Suisse Romande, *Espace 2*, « Tribu », V. Dasen with Laurent Gaspary. 20.2.2015

France Culture, *La fabrique de l'histoire* : « jeux en société », U. Schädler, 17 12. 2014

<http://www.franceculture.fr/emission-la-fabrique-de-l-histoire-jeux-en-societe-23-2014-12-17>

Radio Suisse Romande, *Emission vacarme*, «Retour aux sources : Jouait-on hier comme on joue aujourd'hui? Avec trois fois rien? », V. Dasen, U. Schädler with Cécile Guerin, 8 .12. 2014.

TV /Video/blogs

Archéothéma, 31, V. Dasen and U. Schädler, 21.11.2013

Nyon Région TV, émission ART O'BAZ, V. Dasen, 29.5.2014

RTS, *Couleurs locales*, C. Agustoni, 22.3.2015

RTS, C. Agustoni, U. Schädler, *CQFD*, 30.3.2015

Magic and Play. A Panoply Interview with Véronique Dasen, 20.8.2015

<http://panoplyclassicsandanimation.blogspot.ch/2015/08/magic-and-play-panoply-interview-with.html>

Alma&Georges, “Quand les profs créent des jeux !”, V. Dasen and U. Schädler, 28.10.2015
<http://www3.unifr.ch/alma-georges/articles/2015/quand-les-profs-creent-des-jeux>

Periodicals

Tages Anzeiger, „Dem Spiel gaben sich Frauen und Männer gemeinsam hin“, 11 .7. 2013.

Universitas, “Archéothéma Jeux et jouets gréco-romains“, 12.2013, p. 64.

Unireflets 5, 2013, p. 11

Universitas, Mathématiques et archéologie sur la place publique, 3.2013, p. 60-62.

La Côte, « A quoi jouait le petit Jules César ? », N. Dériaz, 22.5.2014

24 heures, « A quoi jouaient les enfants romains? », M. Schürch, 22.5.2014.

Le Courrier, Musée Romain, Nyon, Veni, vidi, ludique, 25.6.2014.

Freiburger Nachrichten, Carole Schneuwly, «Was Spiele über die Menschen verraten», 2 .8. 2014

La Liberté, Elisabeth Haas, « Les Romains se prenaient au jeu », 11 .10. 2014, p. 32.

24 heures, Christophe Boillat, « Le temple du jeu se plonge dans l’Antiquité“, 10 .10. 2014.

Magazine Coopération n° 45, Ariane Pellaton „Se retrouver pour jouer“, 4 .11. 2014, p. 12-19.

Unireflets, Philippe Neyroud, « Notre culture ludique en jeu », 11. 2014, p. 9.

Echo Magazine, Christine Mo Costabella, « Jeux d’enfants. Les petits Romains jouaient au yoyo», 27 .11.2014, p. 15-

La Regione Ticino, Cristiano Castelletti, „ Il progetto „Veni, vidi, ludique“ indaga il rapporto fra gioco e antichità, Ludi alla meta“, 3 .2. 2015, p. 19.

Murtenbieter „Römische Spiele selbst entdecken und spielen“, 13 mars 2015, page de garde.

La Liberté „Allons jouer au musée“, 13 .3. 2015

6. International conferences

Two international events took place, they both involved visits of the exhibitions:

20-22.10.2014: International conference *Jeux et multiculturalité dans l’Antiquité gréco-romaine*, organised by V. Dasen and U. Schädler, with visits of the exhibition in MSJ and MRN. Publication in preparation. ca 40-50 participants.

5-18.4.2015 XVIII Board Game studies conference, organised by Ulrich Schädler, Musée Suisse du Jeu/Université de Fribourg (V. Dasen), with visit of MRV. ca 70 international participants.

7. Ouputs

Wide audience publication

Catalogues/special issues

C. Agustoni, E. Clivaz, V. Martini, U. Schädler, *Veni, vidi, ludique. Les jeux sont faits!* (Musée romain de Vallon 6), Vallon, 2015 (translated into German)

V. Dasen and U. Schädler, dir., *Archéothéma* 31, 2013, *Jeux et jouets gréco-romains*, with contributions of 15 international specialists, all translated into French by the team (E. Clivaz and V. Dasen):

Austria: C. Behling

France : M. Feugère, I. Hasselin Roux, S. Huysecom-Haxhi, I.-D. Papaikonomou

Germany: C. Fluck, U. Mandel, C. Weiss, E. Zwierlein-Diehl

Grande-Bretagne: E. Cobbett

Italy: B. Caré, A. Campana, C. Lambrugo

Switzerland : M. Fuchs, B. Pfäffli

as well as members of the team: E. Clivaz, V. Dasen, J. Genovese, U. Schädler

E. Clivaz, *Archéothéma* 31, 2013 : Le mystère de la « poupée » de Claudia Victoria, 13.

V. Dasen, *Archéothéma* 31, 2013 : Introduction : jeux et jouets dans l'Antiquité (with U. Schädler) 5-7, Poupées grecques, 8-9, Des hochets pour les plus petits (with B. Pfäffli), 36, Jeux de mains, jeux de vilains ? *La morra*, 37.

U. Schädler, *Archéothéma* 31, 2013 : Table de jeu miniature², 23, Quelques règles de jeu, 27, Les lieux du jeu, 38-41, L'art de jouer aux dés, 46, Le jeu des cinq lignes: Ajax et Achille, 50-51, Jouer aux billes à l'époque romaine, 54-55, A quoi joue-t-on? Les osselets, 62-63, Les jeux de pions, 64-65, Jouer avec la mort: Jeux en réemploi ou inscriptions en forme de jeux? 68-69.

V. Dasen (ed.), *Veni, vidi, ludique. Le jeu de la vie*. Catalogue-leporello de l'exposition, Nyon, Musée romain, 24 mai-31 octobre 2014.

with contributions of E. Clivaz, Ch. Bianchi (Milan), H. Chew (Saint-Germain-en-Laye), V. Dasen, L. Flutsch (Lausanne), C. Lambrugo (Milan), Y. Manniez (Nîmes), N. Mathieu (Grenoble), L. Péchoux (Dijon), U. Schädler.

V. Dasen and U. Schädler (dir.), *Jeux, identité et multiculturalité dans l'Antiquité classique*, Rennes, PUR (in preparation)

Wide audience articles

U. Schädler, « Jeux graffiti: des dessins dans la ville », *Universitas*. Le Magazine de l'Université de Fribourg, n.°4: Dossier Turquie, Juin 2014, 24-25.

C. Agustoni, V. Dasen, J. Genovese, V. Rey-Vodoz, U. Schädler, « Veni, vidi, ludique – Trois expositions autour du jeu et de l'Antiquité », *Archäologie Schweiz, Archéologie suisse*, 2015, 42-45.

Elodie Clivaz, „Tu seras une femme ma fille!“, *Universitas* 4, 2015, p. 19-20.

Also online : http://www.unifr.ch/scm/pdf/uf/2015/uf04_14_15.pdf

Peer-reviewed articles

V. Dasen, 'Achille et Ajax : quand l'agôn s'allie à l'alea', *Revue du Mauss*, 2015, 81-98.

V. Dasen, 'Le destin au bout des doigts', in A. Neumann-Hartmann, Th. S. Schmidt (ed.), *Munera Friburgensia. Festschrift zu Ehren von Margarethe Billerbeck*, Bern, Peter Lang, 2016, 167-175.

V. Dasen, 'Jeux de l'amour et du hasard en Grèce ancienne', *Kernos. Revue internationale et pluridisciplinaire de religion grecque antique*. (submitted)

V. Dasen, « Le hochet, entre soin et jeu », *Annales de démographie historique*, in preparation.

Monography

V. Dasen, *Le sourire d'Omphale. Maternité et petite enfance dans l'Antiquité*, Rennes, PUR, 2015, 408 p. (with two chapters discussing toys and games)

Public and scientific lectures (selection)

14.3.2013, Fribourg University, Presentation of ancient games and toys (block-course), (V. Dasen and U. Schädler)

13.11.2013, Fribourg University, Presentation of Archeothema and of the movies *Veni, vidi, ludique* (V. Dasen and U. Schädler)

20-22.10.2014, International Conference *Jeux et multiculturalité*, La Tour-de-Peilz, Musée suisse du Jeu:

V. Dasen and U. Schädler, « Une koiné ludique en Méditerranée ? Circulation des jeux et processus d'acculturation : questions méthodologiques » (avec Ulrich Schädler), 21 .10. 2014.

U. Schädler, Greeks, Etruscans, and Celts

V. Dasen, "Saltimbanques et circulation des jeux"

V. Dasen, "Jeux et jouets gréco-romains", La Tour-de-Peilz, Musée suisse du Jeu, 14 novembre 2014

07.02.2015, Paris, EHESS, Journée d'étude "Jeu et genre", organised by Véronique Dasen et François Lissarrague : V. Dasen : "Le destin au bout des doigts : le jeu de la morra"

17.4.2015, Fribourg, Board Games studies 18, V. Dasen, "Dicing with Death : Achilles and Ajax",

V. Dasen, invited professor 2015

A series of lectures were given at the University of Angers, spring 2015:

01.04.2015 : Veni, vidi, ludique: histoire et archéologie de la culture ludique

02.04.2015 : Veni, vidi, ludique : la culture ludique antique

A series of lectures were given in a joint seminar *Images en jeux, jeux d'images*, with François Lissarrague, Paris, EHESS :

9.11.2015: "Achille et Ajax : quand l'agôn s'allie à l'alea"

17.12.2015: "Jeux de mains: la morra"

20.11.2015: Journée d'études "Images en jeu, jeux d'images", organised by Véronique Dasen and François Lissarrague. V. Dasen: "Saltimbanques grecs et romains".

27.11.2015 : University of Angers, journée d'étude *Enjeux: « Jeux et jouets gréco-romains »*

U. Schädler (Swiss Museum of Games)

11.2.2014: U. Schädler “Spiele als Indikatoren für Wandel : Das Beispiel Ephesos”, Zürcher Hochschule der Künste

20.2.2014.: U. Schädler, “Ajax et Achille - jouer dans l'au-delà. Un vase grec au Musée Suisse du Jeu”, Musée suisse du Jeu,

7.5.2014: U. Schädler, “Ephèse - métropole antique et ville de jeux”, Musée romain de Nyon

12.11.2014: U. Schädler, “ Spielzeugmuseum Riehen : Der 1. Weltkrieg am Küchentisch. Wie man Krieg im Krieg spielt”, Riehen

19.3.2015: U. Schädler and J. Genovese, “Games in sword-and-sandal-movies”, Swiss Museum of Games

Clara Agustoni (Roman Museum, Vallon)

21.3.2015 : Les jeux sont faits ! Autour de l'exposition du Musée de Vallon, Avenches, apéritifs du Musée romain

8. Major Ouputs

Veni, vidi, ludique was very warmly received by the public and the scientific community. Its non-stop continuation (Paris, 2015, Bavay 2015, Cholet 2016, Vieux-la-Romaine 2017...) demonstrates its successful impact.

Paris, EHESS, 40th anniversary, loan of the knucklebone oracle for: Les fils du destin. Une installation autour du destin et des pratiques divinatoires, 1-18.6.2015

Bavay, Forum Antique (France), 17.9.2015 – 19.1.2016: 7'587 visitors

<http://www.weo.fr/videos/veni-vidi-ludique-la-nouvelle-exposition-du-forum-antique-de-bavay/>

New

Cholet, Musée d'art et d'histoire (France), 30.4-27.11.2016

<http://www.ot-cholet.fr/grand-public/agenda/exposition-veni-vidi-ludique-cholet.html>

La Chaux-de-Fonds, Bibliothèque de la Ville, 4.1.-13.8.2016

<http://www.tempslibre.ch/evenements/veni-vidi-ludique-196215>

Associated with the Festival Ludesco (11-13.3.2016)

Forthcoming : Vieux-la-Romaine (France), 2017

A return in the German part of Switzerland is planned, as well as further travels abroad (France and Germany)

Cholet, Musée d'art et d'histoire, 29 avril 2016

The interest demonstrated by young researchers made us organise a two-day doctoral formation *Jeu et genre* at the MSJ (supported by the CUSO, Etudes genre), April 7-8, 2016.

The positive impact of the project made us decided to prepare an ERC advanced project on ludic culture to be submitted on september 1, 2016.

Other major output concern new collaborations, in particular with the interdisciplinary research programme *Enjeu[x], enfance et jeunesse*, directed by the University of Angers (130 teachers/researchers, 17 laboratories).

<http://enfance-jeunesse.fr/presentation/>

Enjeu[x], enfance et jeunesse thus sponsored a one day workshop in Cholet, Musée d'art et d'histoire when the exhibition *veni, vidi, ludique* opened (april 29, 2016).

<http://enfance-jeunesse.fr/events/journee-detude-accueil-et-soin-de-lenfance-antiquite-moyen-age/>

Forthcoming public presentations in wide circles :

- lecture in the Louvre Museum, Paris :

V. Dasen : « Veni, vidi, ludique : jeux et genre dans l'Antiquité classique », Louvre auditorium, 30.5.2016

<http://www.louvre.fr/veni-vidi-ludique-jeux-et-genre-dans-l-antiquite-classique>

- Fontainebleau, Festival d'histoire de l'art, *Le rire*, 3.-5.6.2016

<http://festivaldelhistoiredelart.com/>

<http://www.sciencespo.fr/projets-collectifs/fr/projet/750>

Table-ronde : « Jouer pour rire ? », with V. Dasen, R. Hamayon, F. Lissarrague, and J. Genovese

Œuvre au crible : « Jeux divins, rire et transgression », with Martine Denoyelle, Louvre Museum

Demonstration of Roman games with E. Clivaz, V. Dasen and J. Genovese

Forthcoming new public demonstration on September 24, 2016, Open day of Fribourg University, at the demand of the University of Fribourg.

9. Measurable output

Number of visitors

Nyon, Roman Museum : 5588 visitors

28.6.2014: Café scientifique, *Rêver les poupées, hier et aujourd'hui*, and demonstration of games: ca 120 participants

Swiss Museum of Games : 8183 visitors

21.10.2014: Café scientifique, “Un regard d’anthropologue, à la lumière des quatre principes de jeu de Roger Caillois”: ca 40 participants.

25.2.2015: Café scientifique, “Jeux de putti, de l’Antiquité à la Renaissance: les jouets en plus”: ca 20 participants.

9.12.2014: Meeting a creator of games, *Cyclades*: 15 participants

20.2.2015: Meeting a creator of games, *SPQRisk*: 8 participants

17.04.2015: Games night in collaboration with the Ludothèque La Tour: 12 participants

Initiations, one weekend and wednesday afternoon per month during the exhibitions.

Organised with the association Ch’PiiL : 7 months x 2 = 14 x 10 participants = ca 140 participants

Vallon, Roman Museum : 6785 visitors

28.6.2015: Café scientifique, and open day with demonstration of games: 232 participants

Römertag, Vindonissa Museum Brugg and Legionärspfad Windisch, 4.5.2014: 3669 participants

(1618 children, 2015 adults)

Fribourg, Jubilee of the 125th anniversary of Fribourg University (2014)

Roadshow, *Jouer comme au temps des Romains*, 2.5-11.10.2014: 4457 participants

Pérolles 2, official Feast of the Jubilee, 20.9.2014: 8000 participants

IX Festival international du film d’archéologie (FIFAN), 23-28.3.2015: ca 1000 participants

<http://www.mrn.ch/fr/festival/edition/en-cours-0-97468>

Forthcoming : Fontainebleau, Festival d’histoire de l’art, *Le rire*, 3.-5.6.2016

ca 32'000 participants in 2015

<http://festivaldelhistoiredelart.com/>

<http://www.sciencespo.fr/projets-collectifs/fr/projet/750>

The special issue of *Archaeothema*, 31, 2013, also contributed to the diffusion of knowledge :

- Print-run : 10'000

- The issue is available printed and on tablets and Iphones. It can be downloaded (free appli on App Store for iOS or Play Store for Android.

- we (V. Dasen and U. Schädler) presented the concept and the exhibition in a video, available on Archeothema website :

<http://www.archeothema.com/numero/jeux-et-jouets-grecs-romains.htm>

Eyetracking experience (prof. R. Caldara, Fribourg University) : the data are not yet available.

10. Description of the content

One project, three Swiss Museums

The project "**Veni, Vidi, Ludique**" was developed at the University of Fribourg by Véronique Dasen and Ulrich Schädler to successively present the results of the latest research on games and toys in Graeco-Roman antiquity in three Swiss museums. From May 2014 until February 2016 each museum presented different aspects of the sources and artefacts, placed in their cultural context. The exhibitions at the three museums share the same common title, but have distinct subtitles according to their specialty:

1. Nyon, Roman Museum: "The game of life", May 24 - October 31, 2014
2. La Tour-de-Peilz, Swiss Museum of Games: "Playing with antiquity" (the reception of antiquity in modern boxed games), October 10, 2014 - April 19, 2015
3. Vallon, Roman Museum: "The die is cast" (on the practice of board games), March 14, 2015 – February 28, 2016

Contents of the three exhibitions

Available free in the exhibition : interactive applications, touchtable and movies

- The **puzzle of Archimedes**. Touchtable by the Arkimedeion Museum, Syracuse. The mathematician Archimedes of Syracuse (3rd c. BC.) has invented this game that looks like the Chinese Tangram. This "puzzle" has 14 different geometric shapes that can match 536 ways to form a square.

- Touchtable game : "**The Knucklebone Oracle**". Roll 5 knucklebones and discover which fate the gods reserve for you. An application developed for the Agora Project. Available on Apple App Store.

- Touchtable game : "**The Loculus of Archimedes**". An application developed for the Agora Project. The goal of this game is, as the Chinese Tangram, to reconstruct, from geometric pieces, varied figures as an elephant, a goose in flight or armed mirmillon. It is based on an ancient description of Archimedes' invention by Ausonius.

- Touchtable game: "**Playing in the city of Ephesus**". An application developed for the Agora Project. It invites visitors to explore an original and playful way the Roman city of Ephesus from different games engraved in the marble floor. For each game, a brief description of the rules is given. This application is based on the results of the research of Ulrich Schädler.

- **7 movies made by F. Vermot :**

- *Pentelitha* <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vl7a9zySKOg>
- *Pleistobolinda*, le jeu « du coup le plus haut »
- *Omilla*, le « jeu du cercle »
- *Nuces castellatae*, les « châteaux de noix »
- Le jeu de la planche
- *Tropa* ou *Orca*, le pot
- Jeu de billes

- « *Clash of the Dicers* », animation created by Steve Simons

<http://www.panoply.org.uk/clash-of-the-dicers.html#.Vk2UitF-Qt>

Nyon, Roman Museum: "The game of life", May 24 - October 31, 2014

- **14 panels:**

- *Veni, vidi*, ludique : « Le jeu de la vie »
- La petite enfance
- Les jouets mobiles
- Les poupées grecques
- Les poupées romaines
- Jeux d'adresse et jeux collectifs
- Jeux sans jouets
- Les jeux de hasard
- Jeux de pions
- Jouer dans la ville
- Les astragales
- Jeux d'hier et d'aujourd'hui : ruptures et continuités
- Panneau remerciements
- Panneau codes QR

- **More about: 13 files**

- Les osselets
- Jeux ou divination ?
- Le jeu des 5 lignes
- La petite marelle
- Le jeu des petits soldats
- Le jeu des 12 points
- Les billes
- Histoire du dé
- Jouer avec des noix
- Le destin de *Iulia Graphis*
- L'envol vers la vie. Les garçons et la passion des oiseaux
- Le chien dans l'Antiquité grecque et romaine
- Jeux immatériels

- **Roman games and rules available in the exhibition area:**

- Jeu des cinq lignes
- La petite marelle
- Le jeu des petits soldats
- Jouer avec des noix
- Le jeu de la *morra*

- **11 QR codes:**

- La petite enfance
- Les jouets mobiles
- Les poupées grecques et romaines
- *Iulia Graphis*
- Jeux d'adresse et jeux collectifs
- Jeux sans jouets
- Jeux de hasard
- Jeux de pions
- Jouer dans la ville
- Les astragales
- Jeux d'hier et d'aujourd'hui

- **4 appli/touch tables games:**
 - Appli « Oracle des osselets » N. Marfurt, scientific direction V. Dasen and U. Schädler
 - Table touch « Loculus of Archimedes », F. Brulhart, scientific direction V. Dasen and U. Schädler
 - Table touch « Loculus of Archimedes», loan from Syracuss, Arkimedeion Museum
 - Table touch « Jouer dans la ville d’Ephèse », N. Marfurt, scientific direction V. Dasen and U. Schädler
- **7 movies by F. Vermot**, scientific direction V. Dasen and U. Schädler
 - *Pentelitha* <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vl7a9zySKOg>
 - *Pleistobolinda*, le jeu « du coup le plus haut »
 - *Omilla*, le « jeu du cercle »
 - *Nuces castellatae*, les « châteaux de noix »
 - Le jeu de la planche
 - *Tropa* ou *Orca*, le pot
 - Jeu de billes
- **« Clash of the Dicers », animation by Steve Simons, loan of Panoply.org**

<http://www.panoply.org.uk/clash-of-the-dicers.html#.Vk2UttF-Qt>
- **10 ,neon panels’ with scenes of game from Pompeian houses**
 - *Erotes* apothicaires
 - *Erotes* portant la massue d’Héraclès
 - *Erotes* jouant au « jeu du diable »
 - *Erotes* musiciens (lyre et double flûte)
 - *Eros* chevauchant un crabe
 - *Eros* sur un char tiré par deux oies
 - *Eros sur un char tiré par deux capridés*
 - *Eros* voletant
 - *Eros* à califourchon sur un autre *Eros*
- **Praxinoscope**, by Valérie Martini
- **Booklet with rules of ancient games available in the paedagogical area**
- **1 catalogue/leporello**

Objects borrowed from Swiss museums and abroad

The Roman Museum, Nyon borrowed objects from several Swiss and foreign museums.

Objects borrowed from Swiss museums (11)

- Lausanne-Vidy, Roman Museum
- La Tour-de-Peilz, Swiss Museum of Games
- Roman Museum, Avenches
- Archaeological Collection of the University of Zürich
- Augst, Augusta Raurica Museum
- Brugg, Vindonissa Museum
- Geneva, Museum of Art and History
- Frauenfeld, Naturmuseum and Museum of Archaeology
- Bellinzona, Museo Civico
- Bern, Historical Museum
- Sion, Museum of History of Valais

Objects borrowed from museums abroad (9 museums)

- Bavay, Antique Forum
- Dijon, Museum of Archaeology
- Autun, Rolin Museum
- Beaune, Museum of Fine Arts
- Lyon-Fourvière, Gallo-roman Museum
- Lyon, Museum of Fine Arts
- Saint-Germain-en-Laye, Museum of National Archaeology
- Milan, Museo Teatrale alla Scala, Sambon's collection
- Reggio Emilia, Musei Civici

- **La Tour-de-Peilz, Swiss Museum of Games: "Playing with antiquity" (the reception of antiquity in modern board games), October 10, 2014 - April 19, 2015**

- **9 panels:**

- Veni, vidi, ludique : « Jouer avec l'Antiquité » (remerciements)
- Instructif oui, mais amusant ?
- Gravé dans le marbre
- *Panem et circences*
- *Veni, Vidi, Vici !*
- Par les dieux de l'Olympe !
- Toi aussi, mon fils !
- *Pecunia non olet* : L'argent n'a pas d'odeur, ou bien ?
- L'Antiquité pixellisée

- **6 QR codes:**

- Etienne de Jouy
- Gladiateurs
- Cirque
- Mythologie
- Politique
- Commerce

- **Booklet on modern games about antiquity**
- **Excerpts from the movie « Ben-Hur » by W. Wyler (1959)**
- **Several modern board games on the Antiquity available in the exhibition area**
- **2 video games (Caesar; Rome : Total War) available in the exhibition area**

The games all belong to the Museum.

Vallon, Roman Museum: "The die is cast" (on the practice of board games), March 14, 2015 – February 28, 2016

- **8 panels:**

- Veni, vidi, ludique : « Les jeux sont faits ! »
- Les jeux sont faits
- Des jeux pour jouer
- Le jeu des 12 points
- Les pions
- Les osselets et les dés
- Les billes
- Panneau remerciements

- **6 QR codes:**

- L'invention des jeux
- Les osselets
- Les jeux de hasard
- Le jeu des cinq lignes
- Le jeu des petits soldats
- Le jeu des douze points

- **7 movies by F. Vermot:**

- *Pentelitha*
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=vl7a9zySKOg>
- *Pleistobolinda*, le jeu « du coup le plus haut »
- *Omilla*, le « jeu du cercle »
- *Nuces castellatae*, les « châteaux de noix »
- Le jeu de la planche
- *Tropa* ou *Orca*, le pot
- Jeu de billes

- **« Clash of the Dicers », animation by Steve Simons**

<http://www.panoply.org.uk/clash-of-the-dicers.html#.Vk2UtITF-Qt>

- **7 Roman games and rules available in the exhibition area:**

- Le *Ludus duodecim scriptorum*
- Le *ludus latruncolorum*
- La marelle
- Le *pente grammai*
- Le coup de Vénus
- Le *pleistobolinda*
- Piste de bille

- **8 watercolors by H. Becquelin:**

- Deux hommes jouant à un jeu de table (affiche de Vallon)
- Cache-cache (affiche de Nyon)
- Jeux de balles entre deux jeunes filles
- Jeu de balle collectif
- Châteaux de sable
- Ricochets
- A califourchon sur une tige de roseau
- Quadriges (affiche de la Tour-de-Peilz)

1 booklet with illustrated rules

The Roman Museum in Vallon mainly exposed objects found in the Roman villa of the site, with loans from two Swiss museums: Vidy Roman Museum, and Avenches Roman Museum.

3. Unexpected outputs

An eye tracking experience took place in the exhibition of Vallon (MRV, 2015). It was conducted by Prof. Roberto Caldara, Brain Mapping Laboratory, with the support of the Research Pool.

<http://perso.unifr.ch/roberto.caldara/>

We selected questions related to scenography that were tested.

1. About a game and its reconstruction

- Do visitors look at an archaeological, fragmentary, object ?
- Do they look for the explanation about its reconstructions and do they read the rules of the game played with it ?
- do they try to play with the reconstructed game placed beside the window case with the archaeological artifact ?

2. Do they see and use the QR codes distributed in the exhibition that provide complementary interactive information to the visitors.

At the entrance of the museum, visitors were invited to use our special glasses equipped with a wearable eye tracker. The observer will wear the SMI Eye Tracking Glasses 2.0, which rely on an instant setup and unmatched binocular eye tracking performance of 60Hz. A movie showing how this device can precisely track the eye movements of the observer in ecological situation can be seen here:

<http://perso.unifr.ch/roberto.caldara/ERC/walk.mov>.

A new pocket-size recorder based on a customized Samsung smartphone allowed us to perform fully mobile in-field research (extra-long) recordings tasks. We collect data from about 20 voluntaries. They visited the exhibition without knowing what exactly is tested. The whole visit was recorded by the camera in the glasses. When they finished, they filled a questionnaire, providing complementary information (sex, age, expertise in the field) and allowing a double-check of the transmission of information during the visit.

Two collaborators were in charge of collecting the data, one specialised in eye-tracking technology, Ms Yingdi Liu, the other specialised in Antiquity and museology, Elodie Clivaz, who worked at the organisation of the exhibitions. The glasses are relatively fragile and the visit must follow a specific order. At Vallon, the visitors were thus accompanied by a member of the museum team.

The results are not yet available.

11. Google Analytics

Browser & OS

May 1, 2014 - Oct 28, 2015

All Sessions
100.00%

Explorer

Summary

Sessions

200

100

July 2014 October 2014 January 2015 April 2015 July 2015 October 2015

Browser	Acquisition			Behavior			Conversions		
	Sessions	% New Sessions	New Users	Bounce Rate	Pages / Session	Avg. Session Duration	Goal Conversion Rate	Goal Completions	Goal Value
	7,875 % of Total: 100.00% (7,875)	81.28% Avg for View: 80.28% (1.25%)	6,401 % of Total: 101.25% (6,322)	67.62% Avg for View: 67.62% (0.00%)	2.48 Avg for View: 2.48 (0.00%)	00:01:52 Avg for View: 00:01:52 (0.00%)	0.00% Avg for View: 0.00% (0.00%)	0 % of Total: 0.00% (0)	\$0.00 % of Total: 0.00% (\$0.00)
1. Chrome	4,267 (54.18%)	91.91%	3,922 (61.27%)	80.22%	1.68	00:01:01	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
2. Safari	1,383 (17.56%)	58.21%	805 (12.58%)	51.27%	4.12	00:03:52	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
3. Firefox	1,123 (14.26%)	74.09%	832 (13.00%)	57.70%	3.00	00:02:17	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
4. Internet Explorer	775 (9.84%)	72.52%	562 (8.78%)	47.48%	3.61	00:02:46	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
5. (not set)	129 (1.64%)	100.00%	129 (2.02%)	37.21%	0.37	00:00:00	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
6. Android Browser	87 (1.10%)	65.52%	57 (0.89%)	63.22%	2.21	00:01:23	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
7. Safari (in-app)	67 (0.85%)	76.12%	51 (0.80%)	61.19%	2.43	00:02:58	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
8. Opera	13 (0.17%)	100.00%	13 (0.20%)	69.23%	1.54	00:00:14	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
9. Mozilla Compatible Agent	10 (0.13%)	100.00%	10 (0.16%)	100.00%	1.00	00:00:00	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)
10. IE with Chrome Frame	5 (0.06%)	100.00%	5 (0.08%)	20.00%	5.20	00:04:48	0.00%	0 (0.00%)	\$0.00 (0.00%)

Rows 1 - 10 of 16

Audience Overview

May 1, 2014 - Oct 28, 2015

All Sessions
100.00%

Overview

Pageviews

Sessions

7,875

Users

6,322

Pageviews

19,524

Pages / Session

2.48

Avg. Session Duration

00:01:52

Bounce Rate

67.62%

% New Sessions

80.28%

New Visitor Returning Visitor

City	Sessions	% Sessions
1. (not set)	1,391	17.66%
2. Fribourg	542	6.88%
3. Lausanne	392	4.98%
4. Zurich	368	4.67%
5. Geneva	314	3.99%
6. Nyon	182	2.31%
7. Bern	160	2.03%
8. Paris	119	1.51%
9. Lille	113	1.43%
10. Neuchatel	101	1.28%

Audience Overview

May 1, 2014 - Oct 28, 2015

All Sessions
100.00%

Overview

Pageviews

Sessions

7,875

Users

6,322

Pageviews

19,524

Pages / Session

2.48

Avg. Session Duration

00:01:52

Bounce Rate

67.62%

% New Sessions

80.28%

New Visitor Returning Visitor

Country	Sessions	% Sessions
1. Switzerland	3,077	39.07%
2. United States	1,277	16.22%
3. France	756	9.60%
4. (not set)	681	8.65%
5. Brazil	338	4.29%
6. China	158	2.01%
7. Italy	137	1.74%
8. Germany	129	1.64%
9. United Kingdom	109	1.38%
10. Japan	107	1.36%

Présentation de l'audience

1 juin 2015 - 10 mai 2016

 Tous les utilisateurs
100,00 %, Sessions

Vue d'ensemble

Langue	Sessions	% Sessions
1. (not set)	2 133	44,38 %
2. fr	741	15,42 %
3. fr-fr	518	10,78 %
4. ru	366	7,62 %
5. en-us	265	5,51 %
6. ru-ru	137	2,85 %
7. en	130	2,70 %
8. fr-ch	110	2,29 %
9. de	61	1,27 %
10. c	56	1,17 %